

EFFICIENCY ENTERPRISE IN THE ECONOMY HELD PLACE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10016130>

Anotation. In this article, how important it is to effectively organize the activities of enterprises, and the result of the activity is directly related to the state and impact on society briefly stated.

Keywords. Enterprise, efficiency, scientific and technical development, modernization, production, production efficiency.

Anotatsion. This article briefly describes the importance of the effective organization of enterprise activities, and the direct impact of the activity results on the state and society.

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Current the country modernization in the conditions of production release efficiency increase, economy of keeping market system and each how of the period important is a requirement.

Efficiency reflects the economic stability and ability to operate any enterprise. The absence of efficiency and positive results in any work, including in the activities of enterprises, can be explained figuratively speaking as a waste of time, energy and resources.

B.A. Abdukarimov., A.N. Jabriev., IR Zugurov in the work "Corporate Economy", socio-economic efficiency is simultaneously the cause and result of increasing production efficiency, successful operation of the enterprise, all-round development of the individual and the use of all his abilities. They expressed the opinion that the direct social effect is reflected in the growth of knowledge and skills, experience and culture of employees, improvement of the population's health and prolongation of life expectancy.

Rostova Yu. I. Foreign firms and enterprises, in addition to increasing attention to production techniques and technologies, pay special attention to product quality and advertising in order to achieve efficiency in their activities. For example, the Japanese company "Omron". to himself "Everyone good life is good the world for" the phrase motto by doing received American "Caterpillar" company slogan "The world each one 48 hours in the corner service show" and the company "Reebok" is "Good in price the phrase" price". motto by doing received

Analysis and results

Science and technology development of enterprises work release activity efficiency in raising important factor being came and even now importance did not lose. This is it from the factor the following roads with use can:

- * Work release and labor mechanization, automation and complex of the mechanization;
- * Basic technological processes robotization;

* Progressive, labor and resources to save directed technological processes to practice input and of them wide use

* Raw material and materials (labor subjects) modern types Create and of them use _

* Work release organize to do, to plan and manage in processes modern information technologies, computing from the technique use

* Work release and labor scientific organize to do

Technology in practice development, including his structural parts importance and role denial doer or incomprehensible the enterprise to find almirahal. However this factor done increase for only desire and of desires alone enough not For this Firstly money funds and another necessary was looking for resources (investments) find, secondly, modern scientific and technical to works specialized scientific research institutes, construction, technological and another scientific institutions with necessary " connecting " connections, thirdly, own scientific technical goals efficiency counting exit is required.

Free market economy transition deep reforms done needs to be increased. All enterprise work release intensifier events done increase necessary. Efficient organize done to the economy transition each bilaterally developed work release forces and work release relations with provided to be necessary

Market relations developed to go with enterprises future working release to develop enough attention give they start To new techniques, development release to renew, new products to master and work to issue necessary tools they send from him besides, organizational conditions and factors, constructors, engineers, workers creative work to do for economic and social motives Create necessary Technician and technological updates, organizational, economic and social factors work of productivity to increase significant influence shows. For this new technique and technologies current to do provide, produce output, labor scientific organize of reaching progressive forms current make it to regulate improvement, labor culture increase, discipline to grow work of the team stability provide it is necessary

In our country of enterprises different fog and from per year grow up going of this proof so it is each one kind of enterprises own efficiency increase ways looking for to find need and of this one series ways is available.

Enterprises work release of activity efficiency increase important from the factors again one as there is work release potential - the main and circulation funds, worker from strength thrift based on, possible as long as more productive to use show can from this except to them itemized work spent, enterprise today's from the owners except previous generation the work of representatives existence with explain can.

Free market of relations formation conditions work release efficiency increasing all of factors influence to do opportunity significant will change. People in the farm structural changes done will be increased. Consumers from demand come out to him can be adapted;

- the people economy important branch - industry, construction, transport and contact high technologies based on modernized;

- world science and technology development level equalized;

- military work release converted;

- various property forms (state, private, shareholding and the team based on ownership) a lot sleepy to the economy will be passed;

- economy of keeping all forms free is developed;

- economy financial will be made healthy;
- country international to communications organic will be connected.

Enterprises work release of activity efficiency in raising organizational and economic factors , including management, are also important instead havet theirs importance work release of scale growth and household of connections complication with increased goes, these factors to the line the first in place, reasonable work release forms create and existing ones improvement-concentration, specialization, cooperation and combination to do input can in management, planning, economic encourage method and forms, enterprise of activity whole household mechanism in improvement is expressed . Enterprise of the leader the work style and methods of science and technology development and market economy suitable coming necessary for example, an enterprise director knowledge, experience and professional qualifications rather simple employees and from department (service) leaders high standing it is necessary aks without, he team necessary way administration take and to success reach and to the image have to be difficult.

In planning of plans balancing, indicators optimal formation of the system is planned goals resources with provision important importance occupation is enough And this own in turn in the enterprise economic activity strengthening, planning and economic calculations and modern computer technique and his plan economic calculations done increasing opportunities good knowledgeable, literate and qualified economists requires a choice.

Enterprise of activity efficient in being work release intensification, development being released of products type and quality increase and the world standards level delivery of the enterprise work release structure improve such as factors are also important place occupies and to this modern car and equipment, modern technologies, development release and labor organize of doing advanced methods use through is achieved .

Regional analysis of the implementation of important performance indicators in enterprises with state participation in Uzbekistan in 2022¹

No	The name of the regions	The number of enterprises that should implement key performance indicators	The number of enterprises that have implemented key performance indicators	
			Number	In percent
1.	Tashkent city	507	232	46
2.	Surkhandarya region	50	26	52
3.	Bukhara region	105	53	50
4.	Andijan region	102	92	90
5.	Jizzakh region	75	73	97
6.	Namangan region	97	90	93
7.	Syrdarya region	75	71	95

¹ Uzbekistan State assets of the Republic manage agency information based on made up . <https://kpi.davaktiv.uz/site/uz/kpi>.

8.	Samarkand region	144	101	70
9.	Navoi region	77	62	81
10.	Kashkadarya region	191	163	85
11.	Khorezm region	57	47	82
12.	Tashkent region	168	169	98
13.	Republic of Karakalpakstan	89	82	92
14.	Fergana region	109	47	82

If we pay attention to the regional analysis of the implementation of important indicators of efficiency in enterprises with state participation in Uzbekistan, in this regard, 168 out of 169 enterprises (98 percent) in Tashkent region, 73 out of 75 enterprises (97 percent) in Jizzakh region), introduced in 71 out of 75 enterprises (95 percent) in Syrdarya region, in addition to seeing the effective organization of work in this regard, the state of implementation of important indicators of efficiency in Tashkent city, Surkhandarya region, Bukhara region average is 50 percent, which indicates that it is not sufficiently implemented.

The above table shows that efficiency indicators are not fully utilized in the enterprises of our country.

Another important factor that increases production efficiency is economy mode. Resources savings fuel, energy , raw materials material and to materials was grow up going demand satisfy main to the source rotation it is necessary These problems in solving industry main - place occupies. It's on the net raw material and fuel and energy of resources efficient to use provides car and equipment current to do it is necessary

Summary

market relations transition whole in the economy, that's it including construction in enterprises efficiency increase with depends issues complex serious understanding and research requires doing. Management systems formation theoretical basics and their concept market economy needs answer giving organizational - economic mechanism seeing exit, construction in organizations of management main to the concept based on management systems efficient action to do take will come

In organizations management efficiency resources efficiency supply improve at the expense of increase can work release efficiency directly management process and management activity effectiveness garden. This is management system improvement and management economy to provide justifies of the company efficiency to increase the economy competitive to be and to growth big influence shows. Market relations development for in management right and short at the time sure to information have to be enterprises in the activity to changes take will come

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